

Fitness for transport of equine animals

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Introduction

Transport of equidae (horses, donkeys, mules and hinnies) can lead to distress, injury or even death if not properly planned and executed. Training the animals should result in easier loading, but even if the animals are familiar with the associated procedures because of repeated transportation events during their life, they still may be stressed due to negative experiences with loading, unloading or whilst in transit. Many risks to animal welfare can be mitigated by providing appropriate facilities and equipment for handling and transportation (also with regard to current weather conditions). Further, adequate training and supervision of the people operating the facilities, handling the animals and driving the vehicle can add to minimise welfare problems. Equidae benefit from being transported in individual compartments, but may be loaded in sociable groups, ideally with their shoes removed (except for long journeys where equidae shall be transported in individual stalls). Horses are prone to respiratory disease if they are temporarily restrained by tethers that prevent the lowering and lifting of their heads (tie animals using quick release hitch knot with a fairly slack lead). Ensuring that only animals deemed fit for their intended journey are loaded is the most important aspect of maintaining welfare throughout this management process, since it is impossible to assure good animal welfare during transport if the animal is unfit. For further information on the concept of fitness for transport, please refer to the **Thematic factsheet 'Fitness for transport'**.

Legal requirements

Council Regulation (EC) No 1/2005 of 22 December 2004 specifies the protection of animals during transport.

'No animal shall be transported unless it is fit for the intended journey [...].'

(Annex I, Chapter I, 1.)

'Animals that are injured or that present physiological weaknesses or pathological processes shall not be considered fit for transport [...].'

(Annex I, Chapter I, 2.)

'However, sick or injured animals may be considered fit for transport if they are: (a) slightly injured or ill and transport would not cause additional suffering; in cases of doubt, veterinary advice shall be sought; [...].'

(Annex I, Chapter I, 3.)

'When animals fall ill or are injured during transport, they shall be separated from the others and receive first-aid treatment [...] be given appropriate veterinary treatment and if necessary undergo emergency slaughter or killing [...].'

(Annex I, Chapter I, 4.)

Method

Before equidae are loaded for transportation, their fitness for the intended journey needs to be verified. The inspection should include an assessment of animal-based health and welfare measures. This will reduce the risk of animals suffering from serious welfare problems or not surviving the journey. Animal-based measures as well as farm recordings shall relate to:

- Injury
- Physiological weakness
- Pathological process

For all cases where there is doubt regarding the animal's fitness for transport veterinary advice shall be sought.

Injury

Animals that are injured shall not be considered fit for transport, except for minor injury where transport would not cause additional suffering. The following section describes conditions related to injury that render animals unfit for transport.

Injury	Description of animal-based indicator	Outcomes rendering animals unfit for transport
Wound	If an animal presents a severe open wound (thoracic, abdominal, cranial cavities), a reopening surgical wound, a large infected wound, a large wound disturbing the integrity of the body surface (skin, mucosa, or muscle severed), or a severe haemorrhage, it must be considered unfit for transport.	E.g. deep or gaping wound, profuse bleeding, open abscess, frostbite, penis injury, fracture
Absence of vital resources (e.g. due to bad ventilation, inappropriate temperature, feed, water)	<p>The absence of vital resources can be assessed by signs of laboured breathing, heat or cold stress, or dehydration;</p> <p>Shivering is defined as the slow and irregular vibration of any body part, or the body as a whole.</p> <p>Visible signs of sweating on the skin are wet animals, dried sweat spots, or salt deposits.</p>	<p>Heat stress: rapid shallow breathing, flared nostrils, unpredictable behaviour and gait, increased body temperature¹, high respiratory rate, high heart rate and profuse sweating;</p> <p>Cold stress: shivering</p> <p>Dehydration: unresponsive to surroundings, rapid and shallow breathing, drinking excessively for extended periods of time, aggression or threatening behaviour if water is present, dark-coloured or viscous urine (with possibly strong smell), abnormal faeces (loose or very hard, absent or infrequent defecation)</p>

¹Normal ranges for body temperature, breathing rate and heart rate for adult horses and donkeys are 37,5–38,5 °C and 36,2–37,8 °C, 8–16 and 12–44 breaths per minute, and 28–44 and 36–68 beats per minute, respectively.

Physiological weakness

Animals that present a physiological weakness shall not be considered fit for transport unless transport would not cause additional suffering. The following section describes bodily states related to physiological weakness that render animals unfit for transport.

Physiological weakness	Description of animal-based indicator	Outcomes rendering animals unfit for transport
Body condition	Animals in poor body condition are more vulnerable to the stressors of transport, which is why extremely thin animals are not be considered fit for transport. Veterinary advice shall be sought if very fat/obese animals should be transported.	BCS = 1 on a scale of 1 to 5: Horse: ewe neck, ribs, pelvis, backbone prominent, rump sunken, skin stretched tightly over bones, cavity under tail; Donkey: ribs and pelvis clearly visible, angular shoulder, backbone prominent, abdomen tucked up, little muscle over hindquarter, cavity under tail
Unable to move independently without pain or to walk unassisted	If a standing animal does not distribute its weight evenly on all four limbs, as indicated by repeated weight shifting between legs or consistently resting one limb, or reluctance to bear weight while walking, it is highly unlikely that the animal is able to move without pain and is thus unfit for transport.	Inability to stand, maintain balance, bear weight on all four limbs, move without difficulty; Signs of lameness: uneven hoof beats, hobbling or limping, head/pelvis raised and lowered when walking, short stride
Exhaustion	An animal showing signs of severe fatigue or exhaustion is not fit for transport.	Indifference to surroundings (unresponsive, 'shut-down', depressed, persistently refusing to eat and/or drink), inability to stand and/or move, stumbling and/or loss of balance when moving, collapse
Non-ambulatory	An animal is considered non-ambulatory when it cannot rise or is unable to stand unaided, but is still alive. An animal presenting such a condition is unfit for transport.	Living animal unable to rise or stand unaided
Gestation status ¹	Females for whom 90 % or more of the expected gestation period has already passed, or females who have given birth in the previous week.	In the last month of pregnancy as calculated by date of breeding and the first week post-partum; Wax-like beads or droplets of milk on tips of teats
Newborn ¹	Foals in which the navel has not completely healed (i.e. scarring of the umbilical wound) must not be transported. Additionally, journeys over eight hours are only permitted for domestic equidae older than four months of age.	Umbilical stump attached, or scab on the umbilical wound visible

¹Provisions do not apply for registered equidae if the purpose of the journey is to improve the health and welfare conditions of birth, or for newly born foals with their registered mares, provided that in both cases the animals are permanently accompanied by an attendant, dedicated to them during the journey.

Pathological process

Animals that present a pathological process shall not be considered fit for transport unless they are only slightly injured/ill and transport would not cause additional suffering. The following section describes conditions related to pathological process that render animals unfit for transport.

Pathological process	Description of animal-based indicator	Outcomes rendering animals unfit for transport
Swelling	Animals showing an abnormal bodily protuberance or localised enlargement which is causing pain are not to be considered fit for transport.	Enlargement of body part causing pain, e.g. abscess
Prolapse	Prolapse refers to the protrusion of an organ that results in an animal no longer being fit for transport.	Any prolapse (vagina, uterus, rectum)
Impaired vision	Blind animals appear disoriented, frightened, stressed and are not fit for transport.	Blind in both eyes
Diarrhoea	Profuse diarrhoea with a severe disruption of the general condition and a high risk of dehydration rendering animals unfit for transport; may be indicative of an infectious disease.	Loose, watery manure, heavy faecal soiling of hindquarters, dehydration
Discharge	Evident purulent discharge is a sign of acute inflammation and/or infection that results in animals unfit for transport. In such cases an animal's fitness for slaughter is questionable.	Evident purulent discharge of eyes, nose, or vulva
Respiratory disorder	Animals with signs of laboured or difficult breathing, often in association with evidence of general distress such as extended head, forelegs spread are unfit for transportation.	Severe dyspnoea, pneumonia, increased breathing frequency, laboured breathing, panting, coughing
Colic	Animals suffering from colic exhibit signs of discomfort or weakness and are not fit for transport.	Repeated rolling (rare in donkeys), lying down, looking at abdomen, restlessness, groaning, profuse sweating, abnormal posture or head and neck position, increased heart and respiratory rate, fever
Aberrant behaviour	A generalised nervous system disorder resulting in aberrant behaviour or dangerous behaviour renders animals unfit for transportation.	Disorientation, forced movements, aggressive behaviour, ataxia, imbalance, circular movements, difficulties in standing, poor general condition, possibly in connection with fever
Malposition of legs	(Congenital) deformity of the legs, or severely overgrown hooves present a high risk for injury and are likely associated with pain, rendering animals unfit for transport.	Inability to stand, maintain balance, bear weight on all four limbs, move without difficulty; Signs of lameness: uneven hoof beats, hobbling or limping, head/pelvis raised and lowered when walking, short stride

Pathological process continued	Description of animal-based indicator	Outcomes rendering animals unfit for transport
Joint alteration	Arthritis is a painful condition that leaves animals unfit for transport.	Inability to stand, maintain balance, bear weight on all four limbs, move without difficulty, swollen joint, fever; Signs of lameness: uneven hoof beats, hobbling or limping, head/pelvis raised and lowered when walking, short stride
Laminitis	Laminitis (i.e. weakening of the attachment of dermal and epidermal laminae, which in more severe cases can result in separation of the hoof capsule from the underlying tissues) is a very painful condition leaving animals unfit for transport. Usually, both forefeet are affected, however, any combination of affected limbs is possible.	Extremely stiff, short-strided gait, forelimbs placed in front of their normal position and weight shifted toward hindlimbs, reluctance to move, hoof may be warm to the touch, in chronic laminitis clinical signs vary from mild lameness to recumbency
Retained placenta	Not fully expelled afterbirth indicates that the animal is within less than 1 week post-partum or long-term metritic disorder.	Visible placenta, fever
Hypo-/Hyperthermia	Animals with a body temperature outside of physiological boundaries are unfit for transportation.	Fever: rectal temperature > 38,5 °C (horse), > 37,8 °C (donkey) Hypothermia: rectal temperature < 37,5 °C (horse), < 36,2 °C (donkey)
Umbilical disorders	The most common umbilical disorders in foals include umbilical hernia, patent urachus, and umbilical abscessation leaving the animal unfit for transportation.	Umbilical hernia: abdominal tissue protruding through a weak spot or gap in the abdominal muscles into underlying skin; Patent urachus: moist/enlarged/swollen umbilical stump, urine/pus leaking from umbilical stump; Omphalophlebitis: swelling and/or discharge at the umbilicus;

Recommendation for inspection

- Each animal's fitness for transport must be assessed prior to loading
- Pain assessment (see Annex) may be used to support decision making on an animal's fitness for transport in connection with painful conditions (e.g. wounds, swelling, colic, joint alterations, umbilical disorders)
- If there is doubt about an animal's fitness for transport, veterinary advice shall always be sought

Annex

Assessment of pain

Assessing the total pain score may be used to support decision making on an animal's fitness for transport in connection with painful conditions (e.g. wounds, swelling, colic, joint alterations, umbilical disorders). Following, pain assessment utilising the horse grimace pain scale is provided. If animals show obvious signs of pain they may not be fit for transport.

Horse grimace pain scale

<p style="text-align: center;">Stiffly backwards ears</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Not present (0) Moderately present (1) Obviously present (2)</p> <p>The eyelid is partially or completely closed. Any eyelid closure that reduces the eye size by more than half should be coded as "obviously present" or "2".</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Tension above the eye area</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Not present (0) Moderately present (1) Obviously present (2)</p> <p>Straining chewing muscles are clearly visible as an increase tension above the mouth. If chewing muscles are clearly prominent and recognizable the score should be coded as "obviously present" or "2".</p>	
<p style="text-align: center;">Mouth strained and pronounced chin</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Not present (0) Moderately present (1) Obviously present (2)</p> <p>Nostrils look strained and slightly dilated, the profile of the nose flattens and lips elongate.</p>	

Figure 1: Description of the six facial action units of the horse grimace pain scale developed by Dalla Costa et al. (2014).

Table 1: Assessment of the total pain score in equines using the horse grimace pain scale (Dalla Costa et al., 2014). Animals showing obvious signs of pain may not be fit for transport.

Facial action unit	Score	
Ears stiffly backwards	Not present	<input type="checkbox"/> (0)
	Moderately present	<input type="checkbox"/> (1)
	Obviously present	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)
Orbital tightening	Not present	<input type="checkbox"/> (0)
	Moderately present	<input type="checkbox"/> (1)
	Obviously present	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)
Tension above eye area	Not present	<input type="checkbox"/> (0)
	Moderately present	<input type="checkbox"/> (1)
	Obviously present	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)
Prominent strained chewing muscles	Not present	<input type="checkbox"/> (0)
	Moderately present	<input type="checkbox"/> (1)
	Obviously present	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)
Mouth strained and pronounced chin	Not present	<input type="checkbox"/> (0)
	Moderately present	<input type="checkbox"/> (1)
	Obviously present	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)
Strained nostrils and flattening of the profile	Not present	<input type="checkbox"/> (0)
	Moderately present	<input type="checkbox"/> (1)
	Obviously present	<input type="checkbox"/> (2)
Total pain score	_____ (out of a maximum of 12)	

References

Dalla Costa, E., Minero, M., Lebelt, D., Stucke, D., Canali, E., & Leach, M. C. (2014). Development of the Horse Grimace Scale (HGS) as a Pain Assessment Tool in Horses Undergoing Routine Castration. *PLOS ONE*, 9(3), e92281. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0092281>